

Statistical properties of a subjective value exchange model

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Abstract

The exchange process of commodities is the essence of market dynamics. Features such as value, price, and satisfaction are commonly interpreted in the field of economics. However, this has also caught the attention of statistical physicists, who view the market as a statistical ensemble. Concepts borrowed from statistical mechanics, such as temperature or entropy, now appear in the understanding of market dynamics. In this context, we developed a microscopic model for the exchange of a basket of commodities. We consider that people value each commodity in an “individual and subjective” manner and eventually decide to exchange them in the market. We computed the statistical distribution of the valued commodities and analyzed the connection between supply-demand and the thermodynamic concept of temperature. The corresponding entropy of the system was also compared to that expected for a microscopic thermodynamic system.

Keywords: exchange value, valuation, econophysics, entropy, temperature.

1. Introduction

Econophysics studies a wide variety of phenomena, encompassing both macroeconomic and microeconomic processes. However, long-term macroeconomic processes generally cannot be considered “in equilibrium” making them challenging to analyze from the perspective of standard thermodynamics (Viaggiu, 2012). In contrast, short-term economic phenomena can be approximated as a “thermodynamic equilibrium state” with a certain degree of accuracy (Viaggiu, 2012; Gallegatti, 2006). In particular, models of goods exchange in credit, financial, or real estate markets exhibit short-term equilibrium fluctuations, with the corresponding conservation of certain quantities.

The earliest successful investigations from the microscopic perspective of exchange are based on the “minority game” model (Gallegatti, 2006; Moro, 2004). This model assumes a constant quantity of goods available in the market. Individuals can buy or sell each good. If there are more buyers, the price of the good increases, and sellers win. Conversely, if there are more sellers, the price decreases, and buyers win.

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The “minority game” model has proven successful in describing a process where the achieved “economic equilibrium” does not correspond to a single state but rather to a “statistical equilibrium” of the system (Viaggiu, 2012). This equilibrium directly results from each individual’s lack of knowledge about others’ future behavior, acting instead on ‘their own expectations’ of what others will do. This is known as the “bounded rationality” of individuals (Moro, 2004).

The “minority game” does not address the issue of the value of goods. A more realistic model should begin with the valuation of one’s own goods relative to others’ and culminate in the expectation of profit from a potential exchange. This expectation of profit drives each agent toward exchange, which only proceeds if all the involved agents benefit with the deal (Mises, 1954).

The valuation of goods is not actually a “measure” but a “comparison” among them. Valuation, indeed, establishes an order of preference between the own goods and others’ goods. This kind of “qualitative scale of values” is always *subjective* and *unique* to each individual.

Our exchange model addresses the subjective-value before transactions. This is a quite different point of view from the “minority game” model and others (see, for instance, Gardner, 1970; Jaffé, 2014 and 2015; Pomorski, 2023; Toscani, 2022). Thus, we first outline the basic framework of the model in Section 2. We then proceed to a quantitative formulation in Section 3. A brief discussion on the economic meaning of our results is exhibited in Section 4. Section 5 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Background

2.1 The framework

Any commodity (good) that comes to the market is valued “as it stands”, accomplishing a *subjective* value (Mises, 1954). This means the following:

- (a) The valuation considers the commodity as indivisible, regardless of whether it is physically divisible. This implies that its marginal utility coincides with its total utility.
- (b) Two physically identical commodities may accomplish different subjective values.
- (c) Two physically identical commodities may come to market as a single batch or as two separate goods. Each will have its own subjective and indivisible value.
- (d) An agent may possess one batch and not possess another batch, both physically identical but of different quantities. The agent will subjectively value each one independently, regardless of whether they possess it or not.

These considerations take place during the *individual* process of valuation, no matter if the commodity is under the own possession or not. However, the own possession can be given in exchange for others' commodity if this action move the agents to a more convenient situation. Thus, the motive for an exchange is the expectation of *benefit*, while a true satisfaction occurs only after the exchange.

Any exchange of commodities is not merely a transfer of possession but also is the way that each individual gets informed about others' valuations. Thus, agents revise their prior subjective valuation of commodities just after the exchange and establish a new order of preferences among commodities (owned and not).

Notice that any new valuation process involves either exchanged commodities and not exchanged ones. A "reversion" of the *subjective* values may occur, since a low-valued commodity may become better valued after the exchange, even surpassing the (subjective) value of not exchanged goods (Mises, 1954).

2.2 The exchange model

The model considers a set of M goods available in the market. These may be labeled as a, b, c , and so on. Recall from Section 2.1 that each label refers to the good or commodity "as it stands" and not after its physical condition. However, any standing commodity may be in one of two states of possession. For instance, a or \bar{a} means that this commodity is owned or not by the individual, respectively.

Regardless of the state of possession, the individual assigns value to commodities. This is some kind of in-mind grading that brings out a preferential order among commodities. The following is an example of preferential order

$$a < \bar{b} < c < d < \bar{e} \dots \quad (1)$$

meaning that \bar{b} is preferred to a , and in turn, c is preferred to \bar{b} , and so on. Notice that valuation (1) stands regardless of the state of possession.

Valuation is an in-mind process, and thus, the above preferential order $\bar{a}\bar{b}c\bar{d}\bar{e}$ is unknown to others out of me. For instance, the following valuations are possible:

$$\text{Me} : \bar{a}\bar{b}c\bar{d}\bar{e} \quad , \quad \text{She} : e\bar{d}\bar{c}\bar{b}\bar{a} \quad (2)$$

She and Me have quite different orders of preference (and possessions). However, if we bring to market our commodities we may exchange them for mutual benefit (Jevons, 1896). The exchange between commodities a and e seems to be the most satisfactory one, since both give our less valuable good in ex-

change for the most valuable one.

Thus, our preferential orders written as the sequence of $M = 5$ letters in (1) undergo the following changes:

- Commodities a and e switch to the corresponding new state of property. In my sequence, $a \rightarrow \bar{a}$ and $\bar{e} \rightarrow e$, while the opposite occurs in Her sequence.
- The given-up commodity updates its valuation to a similar value as the received commodity. Thus, my valuation after the exchange updates to $\bar{bcd\bar{a}e}$, while Her valuation updates to $d\bar{c}\bar{b}\bar{e}a$. Notice that the exchanged goods move to a contiguous subjective value and further exchanges between them are no longer beneficial.

The coincidence of wants somehow informs each partner of the valuation of the other, and consequently, both update their in-mind valuations towards a more accurate preferential order. This movement induces a *reversion* between the given-up good (say, a in my grade) and the intermediate goods (say, \bar{bcd} in the same grade). This is a natural phenomenon since the intermediate goods were less valued than the received-in-exchange good (say, e in my scale) and must remain so (Mises, 1954). The preferential order among the intermediate goods should also remain unchanged.

3. Results

3.1 The subjective model as a thermodynamic system

The subjective-value model can be studied in the statistical context of an *ensemble* of individual micro-states. This means that any in-mind preferential sequence, as introduced in Section 2.2, corresponds to a micro-state of the individual. Examples of possible micro-states are the following (assuming the amount $M = 5$ of available goods in the market)

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{abcd\bar{e}} \\ & \bar{bcd\bar{a}e} \\ & \bar{bd\bar{c}ae} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Each micro-state represents a specific valuation situation for the individual. But valuations may vary due to subjective reasons or to any exchange process. There may be $M!$ possible situations to be accessed, regardless of the state of possession of commodities (see Section 2.2).

Consider an individual owning m goods (out of M available commodities in the market). At any fixed preferential order, all the possible states for owning m goods is the combinatorial number $M!/[(M - m)!m!]$. Thus, the total number of micro-states for the individual, considering both the preferential order and the ownership of goods, is given by

$$\Omega_M(m) = M! \frac{M!}{(M-m)! m!} \quad (4)$$

where the number of goods owned by the individual can be any number in the interval $0 \leq m \leq M$. The magnitude $\Omega_M(m)$ is actually the multiplicity of micro-states for the individual.

Notice that an individual who brings to the market m goods, always keeps m goods in possession, regardless of changing his (her) in-mind preferences or the number of exchanges performed. This means that m is set at the opening of the market, although the individual chooses in every exchanging action which commodities accomplish a better valued portfolio.

Our first milestone in the investigation is that a Boltzmann entropy may be introduced in the subjective value model as follows

$$S(m, M) = k \ln [\Omega_M(m)] \quad (5)$$

where, for convenience, the Boltzmann constant is set to $k = 1$. The function $S(m, M)$ thus defined is consistent with the thermodynamic entropy, as it is an additive and increasing function under certain conditions. Both properties can be easily proved (Huang, 1987).

For a complete understanding of the subjective model as a thermodynamic system, we should now introduce “quasi- infinitesimal” changes in m or M . These changes are considered to be so small (and slow) that the model stands quasi-static (Huang, 1987). The entropy varies as follows

$$\Delta S = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial m} \right)_M \Delta m + \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial M} \right)_m \Delta M \quad (6)$$

This expression is quite meaningful since the first law of thermodynamics establishes that $\Delta U = T \Delta S - P \Delta V$, where ΔU and ΔV stand for the variation of the internal energy and volume of the system, respectively. It is straight forward to associate the number of available commodities M with the volume V of a classical thermodynamic system, and the own goods m with the internal energy U of the system.

Notice that energy is a fixed quantity in an isolated system and the micro-canonical ensemble appears as the right picture for this kind of systems (at constant volume). Thus, the subjective value model may be adequately described within the microcanonical context.

The identification of m and M with a thermodynamic energy and volume allows a formal definition of temperature T and pressure P . Both definitions read as follows

$$\frac{1}{T} = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial m} \right)_M, \quad P = T \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial M} \right)_m \quad (7)$$

We are actually not interested in the pressure at this stage of the investigation. However, temperature is a meaningful magnitude in this context since it represents the “parameter governing the equilibrium between one part of the system and another” (Huang, 1987). See Section 3.2 for more details.

The computation of temperature for small systems can be found throughout the literature (see, for instance, Miranda 2015, 2017).

$$\frac{1}{T} = \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta m} = \ln \left[\frac{M + 1 - m}{m} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta S = S(m, M) - S(m - 1, M)$ and $\Delta m = 1$. This definition of ΔS ensures that $T \rightarrow 0$ when $m \rightarrow 0$, as expected. Fig. 1 exhibits T as a function of m/M .

Fig 1: Temperature vs. m/M for different values of M (see legend).

Note that the temperature in (8) changes sign when passing through the point $m = (M + 1)/2$, although this point is not well defined. This sign change is well-documented in the literature (see Malgieri 2017, 2018; Miranda 2015) and is attributed to the limited number of goods M (say, an energy upper bound).

Our main conclusion from this Section may be summarized as follows: the number of owned goods m plays a similar role as the energy in classical thermodynamic systems. The temperature of the system, however, is a function of the fraction of the number of own commodities with respect to the number of all the available commodities in the market. On the contrary, the in-mind subjective values are neither linked directly to the individuals’ energy and temperature, but affect its entropy (more details in Section 3.3).

3.2 The thermodynamics of exchange

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, temperature is the key magnitude in the equilibrium between different parts of the system. We will show how this is accomplished within the subjective value model.

Recall that the exchange of goods corresponds to the human action of receiving a good and giving up another. This is a single action involving two simultaneous transformations: one operation increases the number of owned goods (say, $\Delta m_+ = 1$), while the other decreases the number of owned goods (say, $\Delta m_- = -1$) (see Mises, 1954). The net result does not change the entropy ($\Delta S = 0$) since the process is reversible and the final number of owned goods equals its initial number. According to the expression (8) this means that

$$\Delta m_+ \left(\frac{1}{T_+} - \frac{1}{T_-} \right) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where T_+ and T_- correspond to the temperature achieved when receiving a good and giving up a good, respectively.

We conclude that the double operation of receiving and giving up commodities keeps the equilibrium in the individuals' portfolio. The equilibrium temperature is $T_+ = T_- = T$ and can be computed as detailed in (8).

3.3 The most probable situation

We noticed in Section 3.1 that the individuals' temperature changes sign at the fraction $m/(M+1) = 1/2$, although we did not attempt to make further conclusions on this point. This Section focuses on a better understanding of this issue.

Recall that individuals bring to market their own goods m for giving them in exchange of other goods. However, people bringing few goods are expected to have fewer possibilities of exchange than people bringing a wider amount of goods. But an extremely wide amount of goods brought to the market neither improve the chances of exchange, since the individual has very few other goods to acquire. Thus, the most favorable exchanging situation seems to be out of these extreme ones.

In the context of the subjective value model, people exchange goods to accomplish a better (subjectively) valued portfolio. This is expected to improve as the possibilities of exchange increases. Thus, the maximum multiplicity of micro-states of the individual is the most favorable situation that he (she) can reach. The condition for the maximum is

$$\Delta \Omega_M = \Omega_M(m) - \Omega_M(m-1) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Fig 2: Entropy vs. m/M for different values of M (see legend).

This condition yields $m/(M + 1) = 1/2$ (see Fig. 2). At this fraction of owned goods, we will see the maximum possible exchanges taking place. Consequently, this appears to be the situation where the individuals feel more “comfortable”, since this situation will allow them to improve the (subjective) value of their portfolio.

The above result is quite meaningful. We will discuss its meaning in the context of Say’s law of markets in Section 3.4.

3.4 Discussion

This Section brings together the conclusions appearing in Section 3 and analyzes them in the context of Say’s law of markets.

We mentioned in Sections 3.1 and 3.3 that subjective valuation is an in-mind process that moves individuals to exchange commodities in order to either satisfy their wants and keep their portfolio accurately valued. Valuation precedes the exchange, but exchange itself requires commodities (or services) ready to change hands. Jean-Baptiste Say noticed this issue and stated:

«A man who applies his labour to the investing of objects with value by the creation of utility of some sort, can not expect such a value to be appreciated and paid for, unless where other men have the means of purchasing it. [... This] leads us to a conclusion that may at first sight appear paradoxical, namely, that it is production which opens a demand for products.» (Say, 1880)

This general law of markets realizes that sellers and buyers are both necessary for abundant exchange to occur (Horwitz, 2003). Furthermore, it suggests that the production and demand for goods can achieve a state of stationary exchange (Hutt, 1974). Both statements agree with our results appearing in

Section 3.

Our analysis actually considers that all the individuals' valuations are stationary and equally possible (*i.e.* micro-canonical ensemble). In this context, we showed that the most entropic situation occurs when the number of owned goods is almost the same as the rest of the goods in the market (see Section 3.3 for details). This is in agreement with Say's law in the sense that supply and demand should balance for an abundant exchange.

Notice that Say's law holds for individuals' supply and demand, but says nothing on the aggregates (Hutt, 1974). This point of view is also present in our model. The condition for owned goods $m = (M + 1)/2$ appearing in Section 3.3 is an example of this perspective.

People supplying or demanding few goods in the market are not expected to be active traders. On the contrary, people with the right balance between supply and demand will be the most active traders. Thus, maximum entropy represents, in the current context, the most probable market situation.

Say's law calls for some kind of connection or coupling between supply and demand (Hutt, 1974). Our model acknowledges this issue by means of the temperature (see Section 3.1). It expresses the degree of coupling between the supply m and the demand $\bar{m} \approx M + 1 - m$. Expression (8) reads $T^{-1} = \ln(\bar{m}/m)$ in terms of the coupling between both quantities. Notice that T^{-1} becomes negative for a surplus of supply and positive for a surplus of demand. The perfect balance between supply and demand (say, $m = \bar{m}$) occurs at $T^{-1} = 0$.

Scholars argue that a dis-coordinated market is able to restore balance between supply and demand according to Say's law (Hutt, 1974). However, this requires to bring or withdraw goods from market. This is out of the scope of our model for now, and thus, people always remain in the same coupling condition.

4. Conclusions

The investigation studies exchanging processes in a simple market from the point of view of statistical mechanics. Our main hypothesis is that valuation of goods is an in-mind subjective process and individuals will eventually exchange goods under the expectation of a benefit.

We derived the statistics for the (subjective) order of preferences for the goods (commodities) in the market. We followed the usual hypotheses for the micro-canonical ensemble and arrived to the entropy function of the system.

Our major conclusion is that the model agrees with the Say's law of markets. This "law" or principle of economics claims that markets sustain some kind of balance between supply and demand. Our subjective-value model accom-

plished this balance by maximizing the entropy function.

We were also able to extend the definition of thermodynamic magnitudes to our exchange model. However, we focused on the meaning of temperature in this context. We noticed that temperature actually informs us on the degree of unbalance between supply and demand in the market. Interestingly, temperature here becomes a positive or negative magnitude, since our model is size limited.

We close the conclusions stressing that Say's law connects supply and demand, but does no claims on (subjective) valuation. However, valuation is the starting point of exchange and is responsible for increasing the multiplicity of states of the system. Our next step will explore situation of uneven subjective valuation of commodities.

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